

NON-DETONATING CHARGES IN POLYMER HOUSINGS FOR SMOOTH SPLITTING OF ROCK BLOCKS DURING PRIMARY EXTRACTION AND SECONDARY CUTTING

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ABSTRACT. In some cases, during the extraction of certain mineral resources, industrial explosives are not sufficiently safe for the environment in terms of generated shock waves, toxic gases, seismic waves, scattering and vibrations. The main reasons for these harmful effects of the explosion are the speed and the mechanism of the chemical reaction of explosive decomposition. The authors have focused their research on a variety of fast-combusting high-energetic compositions, that can fully replace the widely used detonating explosives in the extraction and secondary processing (cutting) of large stone blocks. Samples from polymer containers filled with non-detonating compositions, based on waste gunpowder and metal-containing pyrotechnic mixtures were subjected to field tests. The experiments were performed in real conditions on stone blocks with hardness $f = 16$ according to the Protodyakonov rock strength scale. Depending on the lengths of the blast holes, different charge designs were used.

Keywords: non-detonating blasting cartridges, propellants, smooth blasting, ornamental stone extraction

Introduction

The aims of the experiment are to develop ready-made charges, which during the extraction of rock cladding materials could fully replace industrial explosives and the expensive and risky blasting gunpowder (BGP). These devices should be resistant to external influences. Field tests with non-detonating charges in polymer containers are a new step in the study of the potential capabilities of low-speed energetic compositions for fulfilment of delicate blasting in the extraction of dimension stones. To achieve high economic and environmental efficiency of the products, the authors have focused their research on the creation of simplified production technologies and recipes with cheap and affordable raw materials. According with descriptions of Mitkov (2011), products from the dismantling of unnecessary ammunition were applied as a source of energy in the new generation mixtures.

Knowledge of the theoretical foundations of explosive influence in a solid medium, the differences between the action of high explosives and low-explosives, as well as the processes of crack formation in the rocks, plays a leading role in scientific and experimental activities.

Explosive impact in rock medium

As a result of the detonation of the explosives, a very high pressure of the gaseous products is obtained - up to hundreds of thousands of kilograms per square centimetre. Regarding Mitkov (2007), the explosive gases act on the walls of the explosion chamber. As a result, a shock wave (pressure wave) is generated in the rock. Under the action of that shock wave, two types of stresses arise at each point in the space around the charge: in the radial direction - compressive stresses, and in the tangential direction, parallel to the wave front - tensile stresses. As a result of the explosion, zones of crushing, breaking, cracking and concussion are formed in the rock (Fig. 1).

The radius of the crushed zone depends on the strength and elastic properties of the rock. It also depends on the mass and shape of the charge, as well as on the quality characteristics of the explosive, etc.

The fragmentation zone covers the system of circular and radial cracks in a perimeter of up to 100 radiuses of the charge.

Fig. 1. Blast induced influence in solid medium

The compressive and tensile stresses propagate behind the fragmentation zone, also. Their action is manifested in the displacement of the medium without disturbing its integrity. The action of the pressure wave is reminiscent of the action of seismic waves. This zone of oscillations and shocks covers a perimeter of 100 to 1000 radiuses of the charge (Fig. 2).

During the camouflet action of the explosion, the effects of the blast do not appear on the surface of the medium.

Fig. 2. Compressive shock wave propagation in bench blasting

Concerning Mitkov (2010a), when blasting for destruction purpose, the charge should be positioned in such a way, that its action could reach the free surface. When the pressure wave reaches the open face, it reflects and spreads in the opposite direction as a tensile wave (Fig. 3). The tensile wave propagates towards the centre of the explosion, whereby the reflected wave is superimposed on the end of the falling wave. At a certain distance, the algebraic sum of the stress exceeds the tensile strength of the rock, as a result of which the particle detaches. The process is repeated until the difference between the tensile and compressive stresses exceeds the tensile strength limit. At a corresponding intensity of the initial parameters of the wave, the boundary of detachment from the surface comes to the charging chamber, forming a funnel.

Fig. 3. Effects from compressive shock wave: Reflected tensile shock wave, plastic deformation of the rock, ground vibrations

Crack formation process

The advantage of using high explosives compared to blasting gunpowder is, that the splitting does not rely on the generated gas pressure, but on the well-controlled energy of the shock wave, as reported by Shishkov and Stoycheva (2018). In addition, high explosives are more suitable for simultaneous splitting in more than one direction and are therefore required for key cuts where two perpendicular slits need to be made at once.

Figure 4. Effect of split-blasting

According to the theory (Mitkov and Totev, 2012), the shock energy of the industrial explosives causes a splitting effect in the rock. This is achieved by drilling a series of blast holes in a given plane, which are charged and detonated simultaneously (Fig. 4).

Fig. 5. Superposition of shock waves, as a result of simultaneous blasting of two pre-split drill holes

The resulting shock waves are superimposed along the line between the boreholes, increasing the pressure forces generated in this plane (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Split crack formation as a result of generated tensile waves in the point of collision between two compressive shock waves

The compressive forces induce tensile forces in the rock, which act on the perpendicular plane to the direction of compressive shock (Fig. 7).

Proposed Mechanism – Tensile Failure from Compressive Shock

Fig. 7. Tensile stress, generated by compressive shock collision

In this way, splitting takes place along the line between the holes as a result of exceeding the tensile strength of the rock. The secret of successful cracking with high-speed explosives is based on achieving the optimal balance of the distance between the holes and the specific consumption of the explosive (s.c. powder factor). The tensile strength of the rock is exceeded only in the area of shock waves accumulation, i.e. on the line between the holes.

Splitting with high explosives is not an easy task - if the specific consumption of the explosive is too high, cracking occurs not only along the desired line of separation, but in many random directions. At a lower specific consumption, the splitting is not obtained perfectly, and a large part of the energy of the gaseous products is dissipated in the surrounding rock in the form of cracks.

A serious problem (Fig. 1) in the deposits for rock cladding materials regarding the use of high-speed explosives is their distinctive "brizant" effect on the solid medium. The impact energy of their explosion pulverizes the rock immediately around the borehole - a zone of compression damage or the so-called "crushed zone". It is surrounded by a zone of instability of tension or the so-called "fragmentation zone", where the pressure wave remains strong enough to cause a tensile force exceeding the tensile strength of the rock. Then, the created cracks are prolonged by the generated gas pressures. The intensity of the shock wave decreases with the travelled distance. The "seismic zone" begins where the stresses generated by the pressure wave cannot overcome the tensile strength of the material. Therefore, there is no cracking

in this area - only vibrations. Sometimes, exactly these vibrations are able to cause an unexpected release of stress in the undisturbed rock environment at a great distance from the explosion. Such stress-release usually creates a crack with an unforeseen direction deep in the massif.

Principle of operation of the propellants

Regarding description of Boychev (2018), blasting gunpowder (BGP) is a deflagrating explosive, not a high explosive. The effect on the environment is a result of the pressure, caused by the retention of gaseous products from its combustion (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Mechanism of splitting by blasting with propellants

In practice, this is achieved by igniting the BGP in a suitably perforated and well-closed (plugged) blast hole. The explosive energy, generated by the compressed hot gases, causes the splitting due to overcoming of the tensile strength of the stone.

Experimental part

The observations on the behaviour of the explosive mixtures, packed in plastic housings, were carried out in real conditions of a quarry for extraction of rock blocks with monumental purpose.

Studies of non-detonating compositions

In selecting the appropriate formulations, the results of the laboratory tests of explosive mixtures published by Stoycheva and Shishkov (2019), were used as a starting point.

- **Mixture #1:** "flash-powder composition" 65% KClO_4 + 35% Al (dark) with Oxygen Balance = -1,12%;
- **Mixture #2:** 80% gridded DBP + 20% NH_4NO_3 prills with Oxygen Balance = -7,92%;
- **Mixture #3:** 70% gridded SBP + 25% NH_4NO_3 + 5% Al (dark) with Oxygen Balance = -5,19%;

According to descriptions of Boychev and Asenov (2018), the sound-light pyrotechnic composition (Mixture #1) has high deflagration velocities in a closed space. It reaches a rate of 650 m/s with diameter of the charge 20 mm. When that mixture is sealed in a solid housing and the length of the charge is over 250 mm, it shows a tendency to pass from explosive combustion to detonation. This is not suitable for the purposes of the present experiment. To avoid adverse effects on the rock environment, containers with optimal dimensions, relative to the diameter of the blast holes ($\varphi = 38 \div 45$ mm), were chosen.

Compositions, based on waste smokeless gunpowder and ammonium nitrate (Mixture #2 and Mixture #3) have a lower bulk density and a lower rate of deflagration in closed space, compared to Mixture #1. But, theoretically, they emit about four times larger volume of gaseous products thereof. Ignited in the open space, these two mixtures burn with low speed of the order of 2-5 mm/s. Inserted in the selected hull, they cannot

pass from deflagration to detonation. Also, they show a long period of increasing the rate of progressive combustion.

Actually, when propellant-based compositions are packed in a closed volume, due to the gaps between the coarser-grained ingredients and due to the porosity of the smokeless gunpowder, an enlarged combustion surface is formed. Conditions for the transition from layer-by-layer to convective combustion are created. Mitkov (2010b) reported, that as the pressure in the closed space increases, the speed of the process rises and passes to deflagration. This type of mixtures achieves explosive conversion speeds in the range of 250 to 530 m/s, when the diameter of the charge is up to 20 mm and the initial pulse is not powerful. If the density, the diameter, and the length of the charge increase, a transition of the process into atypical detonation could be expected, according to Boychev (2018). The reasons are the raising of pressure and temperature in the confined volume and the formation of shock wave. This phenomenon would cause additional fragmenting of the rock around the blast hole.

Construction of explosive cartridges in polymer containers

The main aim of the present research is to create ready charges from non-detonating compositions in a rigid waterproof package. The container has to protect reliably the reactive content from external influences. The polymer housing must ensure the initial course of the chemical reaction under conditions of confined space and high pressure, as it is written by Boychev and Assenov (2018). At the same time, the hull must prevent the transmission of an initiating pulse between the devices in one package and the escalation of accidental combustion into a mass explosion, according to information given by Mitkov (2010b). Activation of each "cartridge" should only be carried out by means of a built-in igniter.

For the needs of the experiment, the authors looked for options for a ready-to-use cheap plastic product that has a strong body with an inner diameter of about 20 mm and a length of about 150 mm. Its construction must allow easy and reliable airtight closure. The authors focused on the blanks for the production of bottles for carbonated drinks, with a screw cap closure. The so-called "Preforms" are made of durable polymeric material (polyethylene terephthalate) and have the necessary strength characteristics for our experiments (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Construction of the plastic container for explosive charges

Ten containers were filled with each of the prepared mixtures. The three types of compositions have different grain sizes of the components and therefore perform different bulk densities. Thus, the amount in a full container of Mixture #1 was 0,050 kg, of Mixture #2 was 0,030 kg, and of Mixture #3 was 0,032 kg. For ignition, ordinary electric igniters for pyrotechnic purposes with smooth burning of the fuse-head were chosen. The igniter was placed in the middle of the bulk charge. The electric wires were passed through a small hole in the screw cap, which was filled and sealed with hot silicone after closing the container. The ready samples were used for preparation of decoupled multi-deck chained charges - with air gaps in larger diameter blast holes.

Construction of the charges in the blast holes

Field tests of the prototypes were made in a quarry for extraction of stone blocks from magma rocks. The hardness coefficient of the rock was $f = 16$ according to Protodyakonov. To compare the effect of blasting of the three different mixtures, it was necessary to test them under approximately the same conditions. Rock formations with three open surfaces and a cleft-plane on the fourth side (or four open surfaces) were selected. Two parallel vertical blast holes with a length of 1.80 m and a diameter of $\varphi = 38 \div 42$ mm were drilled in each of the three rocks. The distance between the two blast holes was not more than 0.60 m. So, the value of the compressive stresses in the collision zone between the two charges was sufficient to create perpendicular tensile stresses. Those tensile stresses should form a connecting crack between the holes. Under the influence of expanding gaseous products, this crack could propagate evenly to the free surfaces that are perpendicular to its plane.

Fig. 10. Configuration of the explosive charge inside the blast-hole

To determine the mass of the charge in an explosive hole, practical data, information from literature sources for calculating the parameters of smooth blasting and

experimental results of past splitting with BGP at the same quarry were used. The weight of the charge in one linear meter of contour drilling was determined depending on the type of rocks and the characteristics of the explosive. Regarding data from Stoyanov (1994), when working in solid rocks with a hardness coefficient $f = 16$ according to Protodyakonov, a linear mass of up to 0.300 kg/m is accepted for industrial explosives with normal power. Under the same conditions, the so-called "Specific cost for the formation of one square meter of swath crack" is 0.500 kg/m², and the recommended distance between the contour blast holes with a small diameter is 0.5 - 0.6 m.

The authors decided to reduce the calculated linear mass of the charge by 50 to 70%, because, for the conditions of the current experiment, a smaller diameter of the blast holes was used and the aim was not smooth blasting, but to create a cut with walls protected from cracking. Thus, a linear mass of 0.150 kg/m was determined for Mixture #1, and 0.100 kg/m for Mixture #2 and Mixture #3, respectively. The calculated amount of charge from Mixture #1 was 0.270 kg for an explosive hole, and from Mixture #2 and Mixture #3 - 0.180 kg. The reason for this difference is theoretically the higher performance of the compositions that contain smokeless gunpowder.

Chained decoupled multi-deck charges of five explosive cartridges with the same content were placed in each blast hole (Fig. 10). They were completed by twisting the electric cables, leaving an air gap of 0.10 - 0.12 m between the containers. Thus, the total length of each ready "garland" was 1.30 m. After the chains were hung in the blast holes, thick paper plugs were placed and a reliable 0.60 m long inert stemming was built in. The wires of the five chained cartridges were connected in a parallel circuit. The electric blasting circuits from the two adjacent holes with equal charges were connected in parallel to the main cable. Three experimental blasts were carried out - each with the same construction of the charges, but from the respective explosive mixture.

Results and discussion

The use of chained charges without an intermediate stemming allows an even distribution of the explosive gas pressure along the entire length of the blast hole. Thus, the compressive stresses on the walls of the hole are the same and the chance of forming a crack in unwanted direction becomes smaller.

During the experimental splitting with the sound-light pyrotechnic composition Mixture #1 (Fig. 11) an excellent cracking of the rock body in the intended direction was observed. There was a significant displacement of the treated block, also. Due to the smaller diameter of the hulls, the charges do not have close contact with the walls of the blast hole and the air between them plays a buffer role by reducing the blasting effect on the rock. No parasitic cracks were observed on the detached surfaces.

Fig. 11. Experimental rock splitting by blasting with Mixture #1

In the experimental blasting with Mixture #2 (Fig. 12) a good crack of the rock body in the intended direction was observed, but with a slight displacement of the treated block. Immediately after the explosion, short bursts of flame were noticed through the newly formed crack in the rock. Due to the effect of progressive combustion of the smokeless gunpowder, the smaller diameter of the charges (related to the diameter of the blast hole) played a negative role on the acceleration of the chemical reaction in the volume of the individual charge. During the initial inflammation of the nearest particles of grinded gunpowder by the electric igniter, hot gases were released. That increased the pressure in the hull of the device and began to quicken the combustion process in the remaining volume of the composition. This, in turn, caused the plastic housing to open. So, the pressure dropped sharply. Unlit grains of the composition spilled into the wide volume of air spaces in the blast hole. As a result, attenuation of the deflagration and transition to low-speed combustion occurred. That's why, a very low efficiency of the prototypes with Mixture #2 was shown, despite of the four times larger release of gaseous products compared to Mixture #1.

Fig. 12. Experimental rock-splitting by blasting with Mixture #2

The effect of the experimental blast with Mixture #3 (Fig. 13) was slightly better, but similar to that, described for Mixture #2. The added aluminium increased the temperature and rate of the explosive conversion. The higher velocity managed to react a bigger quantity of the charge. But, spillage of a mixture from destroyed hulls and decreasing pressure in the explosive chamber were observed here again. There was a smooth split, but insufficient expansion of the crack, as well as some residual flames.

Fig. 13. Experimental rock-splitting by blasting with Mixture #1

Conclusions

The results from the field tests of decoupled chained charges with Mixture #1 proved, that the optimisation of the technique for application of "flash-powder" pyrotechnic compositions, packed as ready charges in polymer housings is successful. Such non-detonating explosives can fully replace industrial explosives and blasting gunpowder (BGP) in the extraction and secondary processing of large stone blocks. The relatively high cost of the product is a disadvantage. It could be compensated by the reliefs in the mode of acquisition, transportation, storage and use which result from the lower hazard class of the products.

In terms of striving for lower costs, Mixture #2 and Mixture #3 contain the cheapest possible high-energy components -

ammonium nitrate prills and secondary smokeless gunpowder. This gives a potential for high economic and environmental efficiency of the non-detonating explosive cartridges. The generation of several times larger volume of gaseous products from these two mixtures, compared to Mixture #1 and BGP, guarantees significantly better performance of their charges in case of high deflagration rates. Owing to good performance, the relative cost of explosives can be reduced, and this will contribute to even higher economic efficiency of blasting. The results of the in-situ blasts show that additional research and field tests are needed to increase the efficiency of these charges. The authors are planning to continue their research in two directions:

- testing of the current construction of the products in conditions of multi-deck charges with an intermediate inert stemming of dry sand, which will seal the space around the cartridges and prevent spillage of the composition and decreasing of pressure;
- designing of changes in the construction, to increase the strength of the initial ignition pulse and to enlarge the initial area of combustion inside the charge.

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